

Fostering Critical Thinking Dispositions in Multicultural Language Classrooms: Challenges and Strategies

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Abstract: This narrative review attempts to explore critical thinking dispositions that are essential for effective foreign language learning within multicultural educational environments. It examines key dispositions and highlights pedagogical strategies that support development. Findings of this review reveal that though traditional teaching methods have focused on rote memorization and have aided in language acquisition, they often fall short in nurturing higher-order critical thinking skills. This review highlights the influence that cultural context has on a student's comfort and participation in critical thinking activities. Institutional barriers also exist including exam-focused curricula and limited training for instructors. Addressing these issues will require increased professional development programs equipping educators with tools needed for culturally adaptive pedagogy and providing flexibility to integrate critical thinking frameworks in curriculum. Adopting culturally responsive, and disposition-focused approaches that offer pathways for educators will create an inclusive learning environment that can engage both language proficiency and complex cultural landscapes.

Keywords: Critical Thinking, Narrative Review, Multicultural Language

Developing critical thinking dispositions in foreign language learning has continued to gain significant attention as educators strive to cultivate skills beyond linguistic competencies. These competencies include fostering cognitive flexibility, analytical reasoning, and open-mindedness in students (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, & Gainen, 1995). From early on, children are able to develop an autonomous theory of mind, an insight in which they view themselves as a “being which can think” (Olson, Astington, & Harris, 1988). Facione et al. (1995) defines the ideal critical thinker as one that consistently demonstrates curiosity, possess a solid base of knowledge, trusting in logical reason, remaining open when evaluating differing perspectives. They are honest when acknowledging personal biases, cautious in forming judgements, and will reconsider their views when needed. The ideal critical thinker maintains clarity, approaches complex problems using structured organization, and they are diligent in gathering information (Facione et al., 1995) Furthermore, they apply criteria in a thoughtful manner, are focused in inquiry, and persistent in achieving results as accurate as possible. Critical thinking facilitates problem-solving and higher-order decision-making in both academic and real-world contexts. As world economies continue to expand, the demand for adaptable, multilingual individuals who can analyze content, construct logical arguments, and communicate effectively is growing.

This narrative literature review will examine the theoretical frameworks and pedagogical approaches that support critical

thinking dispositions. It will specifically focus on the role of cultural influences that shape these dispositions. Due to the educational challenges posed by teaching foreign language students with diverse cultural values and learning styles, this research seeks to analyze how traditional and innovative teaching methods support critical thinking. Furthermore, this paper also aims to identify effective strategies and to explore how these dispositions, shaped by cultural factors, impact student success in language acquisition. The review will address the question: What are the vital pedagogical approaches in foreign language learning that influence critical thinking dispositions in multicultural settings?

Conceptual Framework

DISPOSITIONAL THEORY AND CCTDI FRAMEWORK

Dispositional theory posits that critical thinking is driven not only by one's cognitive skills but also specific attitudes or dispositions that motivate them to engage in complex ideas. Perkins, Jay, and Tishman (1993) discussed that the theory emphasizes that dispositions seem to provide the foundation for consistent and thoughtful engagement in critical analysis. Dispositions are essential traits that encourage individuals to apply cognitive skills to the fullest extent, creating active and reflective mindsets. This suggests that these traits are not innate but must be nurtured through education and conducive environments (Perkins, Jay, and Tishman, 1993). The focus on cultivating dispositions makes this theory particularly relevant in diverse learning settings (Engberg & Hurtado, 2011). Block and Block (1980) highlight that the

development of critical dispositions is closely related to what they define as ego-resiliency, or the ability for an individual to alter his/her modal perceptual and behavioral functioning in adapting to situational constraints.

In 1995, Peter A. Facione developed the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) to bring dispositional theory into use for practical applications. The CCTDI framework assessed seven key dispositions that align with effective critical thinking, offering a structured way to measure whether individuals are inclined to engage thoughtfully with new information. Based upon the APA Delphi Report on critical thinking, CCTDI operationalizes dispositional theory by quantifying critical thinking dispositions (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, & Gainen, 1995). Through these dispositions, educators can identify strengths in learners as well as areas for development. This allows instructors to create tailored instructional methods to assist in fostering more a critically engaged mindset among learners.

Dispositional theory and the CCTDI framework offers a comprehensive view of critical thinking that reaches far beyond rudimentary cognitive abilities to include motivational attitudes necessary for critical engagement (Facione et al., 1995; Paul & Elder, 2007). This combination supports holistic approaches to critical thinking development. This is even more important in language learning, where being open to cultural diversity, curiosity, and intellectual persistence are crucial for success (Zhang, 2010).

BLOOM'S TAXONOMY

Originally developed by Benjamin Bloom in 1956 (revised in 2001), Bloom's Taxonomy organizes cognitive skills into a hierarchical order. This is structured into six levels, from basic cognitive processes to more advanced ones, representing a gradual progression in cognitive complexity.

Remembering is considered the foundational level of Bloom's Taxonomy. The first scale involves recalling facts and basic rote concepts such as vocabulary and grammar. This stage is crucial for building knowledge, requiring simple recognition or material without necessitating deeper understanding (Krathwohl, 2002). According to Anderson and Krathwohl (2001), this stage requires students to retrieve information from memory. This is often measured through tasks such as rote memorization, multiple-choice testing, or flashcards, reinforcing foundational knowledge through retention (Reeves, 1990).

Understanding is the ability to explain ideas or concepts, interpret meanings, or summarizing texts. At the level of understanding there is an indication of comprehension of knowledge beyond simple recollection as students process and integrate information meaningfully (Krathwohl, 2002). The revised version of Bloom's Taxonomy categorizes understanding as demonstrating knowledge through explanations and descriptions (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). In addition, Shaw (2014) emphasizes that at this level, students are able to paraphrase or give examples, showing their ability to grasp material well enough to discuss it, essential to building connections across various subjects.

Applying is how students use knowledge in new situations, for example, engaging in conversations or writing sentences. Students implement or execute procedures to solve problems, making this level essential for skill development (Krathwohl, 2002). In addition, Anderson and Krathwohl (2001) explain that applying is a transition from theoretical understanding to practical usage, where students demonstrate their understanding or employ concepts across contexts. Moreover, Reeves (1990) describes it as using learned knowledge to engage real-life applications, case studies, or simulations.

Analyzing involves examining and identifying patterns, connections, and implications (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Analyzing enables students to dissect content critically, supporting logical reasoning and insight. Gilbert (1992) adds that analysis often enhances student's ability to evaluate concepts systematically, and is invaluable for advanced problem-solving.

Evaluating critically assess arguments, evidence, and conclusions (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). In Bloom's revised taxonomy, evaluating is considered an advanced cognitive skill requiring learners to assess the validity and relevance of information (Krathwohl, 2002). Shaw (2014) notes that evaluating enables a student to support their own opinions with evidence, thus facilitating critical decision-making and enhancing intellectual rigor.

Creating builds innovative thinking, where learners design or construct new content or solutions from existing knowledge thus producing original work or new expressions using a second

language. This is thought of as the highest level of Bloom's Taxonomy and involves synthesizing information to generate new ideas or products (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). This cognitive skill involves putting elements together in novel ways, including designing experiments or writing original compositions. Kastberg (2003) highlights that the role of creativity in classrooms is essential for fostering innovation and higher-order thinking skills. This emphasizes that creating can challenge students beyond learned or rote information, constructing new concepts or artifacts.

Regarding critical thinking application, Bloom's Taxonomy helps in fostering development of dispositions as learners progress through its stages. As individuals become increasingly curious about language structure and cultural contexts, they seek deeper understanding through exploration and questioning. In addition, learners must remain open-minded to alternative interpretations and cultural perspectives at higher levels of thinking. Bloom's Taxonomy encourages learners to recognize their limits of knowledge as they progress. This assists in developing intellectual humility as they realize higher-order tasks.

PAUL AND ELDER MODEL

The Paul and Elder model emphasizes that critical thinking is not only a set of acquired skills but it is also intellectual practices requiring the use of traits and standards that guide thinkers in reasoned judgment. It integrates elements of thought, intellectual standards and virtues to promote comprehensive reasoning

(Elder, 2008). Elements of thought are a central part of the Paul and Elder framework, and function as building blocks to critical thinking. Each of the eight elements of thought act as a progressive step in reasoning, creating a structured approach to analyzing and synthesizing information. They are as follows:

1. The ultimate objective or goal behind a thinking process is purpose. Understanding what the purpose is helps learners to maintain focus and clarity throughout analysis.

2. Being able to find what the question at issue is encourages thinkers to define the scope and relevance of their inquiry.

3. Using evidence, data, or facts to gather information to consider reasoning. Evaluating information critically to ensure that it is accurate and relevant to the problem.

4. Being able to interpret and infer enough to form reasonable conclusions emphasize the use of logical connections and coherence.

5. Using ideas, theories, and principles to form concepts in order to frame the interpretation and ensure thinking is grounded in solid theoretical bases.

6. Questioning assumptions that might reveal biases or beliefs to improve the reliability of reasoning.

7. Assessing potential implications and consequences encouraging foresight and consideration of broader impacts.

8. Recognizing the point of view from which reasoning is being approached. This is crucial in that it acknowledges multiple perspectives, providing more comprehensive understandings.

With each of the eight elements being addressed, the Paul and Elder model insists that each of these meet specific intellectual standards to ensure reasoning (Elder, 2008). Elder argues these standards include that clarity of thought is visible; information is accurate and free of errors; detail is precise enough to convey specificity; information maintains relevance to issues being addressed; there is enough depth to address complexities; the breath is able to consider differing views and opposing perspectives; it is logical in maintaining consistency; the issue being addressed is significant; and that there is fairness in evaluating the issue.

CALIFORNIA CRITICAL THINKING DISPOSITION INVENTORY

Facione, Sanchez, Facione, and Gainen (1995) note that the California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) classifies critical thinking dispositions into a grading structure of seven measurements based on the APA Delphi Report: Inquisitiveness; Open-Mindedness; Systematicity; Analyticity; Truth-Seeking; Self-Confidence; Maturity.

Inquisitiveness is defined as one's intellectual curiosity and desire to learn even when knowledge applications seem to be unclear (Halx & Reybold, 2005). Facione et al. (1995) asserts that inquisitiveness encourages students to ask questions, seek explanations, and embrace discovery. Furthermore, Tishman, Jay, and Perkins (1993) describe inquisitiveness as an essential component that motivates learners to engage in new content that enhances comprehension and retention.

Open-Mindedness addresses the ability of a critical thinker to be tolerant of diverging views, allowing individuals to remain sensitive to them while remaining aware of personal bias (Lampert, 2007). This is crucial to understanding what others think about similar issues in a pluralistic, multicultural society (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, Gainen (1995). In multicultural classrooms, open-mindedness allows students to appreciate diversity, making them better equipped to engage with content that extends cultural and ideological boundaries (Engbar & Hurtado, 2011).

Systematicity measures one's ability to be organized, orderly, focused, and determined in questioning (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, Gainen, 1995). It is thought that having the ability to approach issues in a way that is focused and has order is instrumental in being competent to focus on questioning before finding solutions. Lee and Mak (2018) emphasize that this disposition supports thoroughly exploring complex problems. Carrel (1989) argues that its role in metacognitive awareness allows learners to evaluate individual thought processes, thus directly refining their approaches accordingly.

Analyticity values the application of using reason and evidence to solve problems and being able to anticipate potential conceptual or practical challenges, intervening when necessary (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, and Gainen, 1995). Analyticity allows one to evaluate arguments carefully, finding logical connections and inconsistencies. Tishman, Jay, and Perkins (1993) argue that analytical thinkers rigorously scrutinize information. According to Norris (1989), analyticity is essential to identifying biases and flaws in reasoning. Perkins et al. (1993) highlights that it is essential to foster thoughtful judgements by breaking down complex ideas into digestible components.

Truth-Seeking is contextualized as the eagerness to seek the best knowledge in given contexts; individuals thrive on asking questions, and they are honest and objective in chasing inquiry (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, Gainen, 1995). Paul and Elder (2007) note that truth-seekers prioritize objective analysis over their own bias, allowing them to excel at balanced reasoning. In addition, Halx and Rebold (2005) argue that truth-seeking tends to drive critical thinkers to remain vigilant against misinformation and superficial conclusions. Lampert (2007), notes that in truth-seeking learners seek the best source of knowledge in given contexts. They are also courageous in questioning, showing honesty and objectivity when findings do not support their original thoughts.

Self-Confidence measures the degree of trust an individual will place in their reasoning methods (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, and Gainen, 1995). Self-confidence allows an individual to trust the

soundness of their judgement, encouraging other to make rational resolutions without relying on external validations (Facione et al., 1995). Perkins et al. (1993) further describes self-confidence as key to independent thought. Zhang (2010) notes that self-assured students engage more deeply with complex content, showing the impact on metacognitive processes in language learning.

Maturity targets dispositions such as being judicious in making decisions. Mature individuals are characterized by how they approach problems, questions, and make decisions while being cognizant of how they are structured (Facione, Sanchez, Facione, Gainen, 1995). Tishman et al. (1993) highlights how maturity is essential for cultivating a tolerance for diverse perspectives. Additionally, Lee and Mak (2018) emphasize that mature learners are much more adaptable and reflective than those without strong critical thinking skills.

By integrating seven CCTDI into language acquisition, learners develop critical thinking and language mastery dispositions. For example, truth-seeking and inquisitiveness encourage students to inquire about the meanings of new words, phrases, and cultural expressions. Systematicity and analyticity assist in breaking down language structures, analyzing grammatical patterns, and finding systematic ways to learn language. On the other hand, self-confidence assists as language learning skills are built. When confidence is developed the ability to communicate effectively increase, leading to motivation for further language learning. Moreover, maturity helps in navigating linguistic and cultural complexities found in second language learning, fostering

balanced and reflective approaches towards language use.

Lampert (2007) notes that acquisitions of dispositions actually vary based on the discipline that students concentrate in. She goes on to explain that for students of humanities, letters, and language, the students scored high within truth-seeking and open-mindedness. Art students engage in reflective thinking and inquiry while creating and discussing artwork. With that said, art students were shown to be weaker in systematicity, indicating the need for guidance in organizing and fostering inquiry. Business and communication students tended to score the lowest of all fields in inquisitiveness, truth-seeking, and open-mindedness.

APPLICATION TO LANGUAGE LEARNING

Dispositional theory and CCTDI framework offers valuable insights into critical thinking in language learning by emphasizing fundamental attitudes that drive thoughtful engagement and cultural awareness. More specifically, the CCTDI applies Dispositional theory in practical ways for educators to evaluate whether students are inclined towards curiosity, careful analysis, and open-mindedness. Inquisitiveness embraces curiosity regarding vocabulary, idioms, and cultural expressions, allowing students to move towards more profound understandings (Halx & Reybold, 2005). In language studies, inquisitive learners tend to ask more questions and seek explanations that help to enrich comprehension and retention.

Open-mindedness is similarly crucial in enabling students to embrace diverse cultural perspectives and linguistic nuances.

Engberg and Hurtado (2011) suggested that open-mindedness is indispensable in multicultural contexts. Being open-minded encourages learners to appreciate different viewpoints and adjust to various cultural norms. Students become better equipped to interpret idiomatic expressions and understand the subtleties of language use.

Systematicity and analyticity enhance language acquisition by promoting structured learning approaches and careful content evaluation. Carrell (1989) explains how systematic thinking helps students organize their study methods while being analytic enables them to dissect language patterns critically. These qualities work in tandem to strengthen language mastery, identify grammar rules, recognize syntactic patterns, and apply these structures in practical contexts.

Self-confidence and maturity support language learners as they apply their skills in real-world interactions. Zhang (2010) notes that confident learners tend to engage more readily with complex language material. This results in an increase to building resilience and independence among learners. Similarly, Maturity allows students to recognize that language acquisition is a gradual process that requires patience as well as a tolerance for ambiguity. Mature learners handle complex linguistic situations with balance and adaptability, which are essential for navigating diverse cultural and communicative settings (Facione et al., 1995).

Furthermore, Dispositional theory and the CCTDI framework seem to support a holistic approach to language education. Through cultivating CCTDI dispositions, educators are able to

assist students to achieve language proficiency to become more adept at communicating.

Fundamental Pedagogical Approaches for Developing Critical Thinking Dispositions

TRADITIONAL APPROACHES

In the past, traditional approaches, such as grammar translation and rote memorization, have been the most widely used methods in language education. However, these have been criticized for their limitations in developing critical thinking dispositions. Macaro (2006) argues that methods focusing on memorization of vocabulary and grammar rules hinder growth of analytical skills and critical engagement. While these approaches do provide foundational understandings of language structure, ultimately, they do not encourage students to question, analyze, or connect linguistic content to broader contexts (Cummins, 2009). Facione, Sanchez, Facione, and Gainen (1995), express that rather than focusing on exercises or exams in which students embrace arguments supported by nothing more than preconceptions, instructors should structure them in ways that reward students based on objectivity.

Dweck & Bempechat (1980) advocate for differing approaches to teaching based on two distinct learning styles of students, entity and incremental learners. Dweck defines entity learners as those who conceive understanding as occurring in a large chunk, with the point of view of either getting it or not – towards novel topics. Conversely, incremental learners conceive understanding

as acquired in increments, they tend to persist in learning, and gradually build their understanding of difficult topics. Entity learners view intelligence as unchangeable, while incremental learners are more proactive in their belief asserting the importance of responsiveness.

Additionally, there are questions relating to the amount of time that is required to provide noticeable instruction to students, this is exacerbated when taking into account ineffective teaching methods with cultural diversities. Considerations must be taken regarding relationships between formal or foundational knowledge (Bunch, 2013). It is also argued that a teachers general knowledge of language may not be enough to effectively convey second language to learners, opposed to individuals that have deep understandings of cultural dynamics of first languages.

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

In contrast, inquiry-based learning (IBL) and reflective practices have become innovative approaches by demonstrating the potential to promote critical thinking dispositions in students. Inquiry based learning is a practice that is considered transformative in that it pushes students to become active participants in their intellectual growth (Lee & Mak, 2018). When students engage in IBL they are challenged to ask questions, seek deeper understandings, and confront uncertainties. Gu, Wang, and Mason (2017) argue that IBL immerses students, igniting their natural desires to explore concepts beyond superficial levels. With that said, Lee and Mak (2018) argue that the success in IBL often hinges on the ability

of educators to frame questions and guide discussions in a way that encourages the engagement of students. If the instructor cannot engage their students, inquiry-based learning becomes at risk of being seen as superficial exercises rather than meaningful exploration of knowledge.

Reflective practices, in the past have been underestimated in how they facilitate critical thinking (Carrel, 1989). However, studies have shown that the use of self-reflection assist students in achieving profound levels of metacognitive awareness. These practices are not just a form of exercise, they are crucial moments for students to pause, challenge assumptions, and consider their approaches. Martinez (2006) goes on to suggest that when students take the time to reflect, they increase their intellectual humility – opening themselves up to new insights. Taking the time to reflect on a situation to examine perspectives is vital to developing maturity in problem solving. Learners also become more adaptable and capable at handling increasingly complex issues. Students can also act as resources for each other through the use of peer evaluations. Moreover, reflective practices encourage students to shift from reactive ways of thinking towards more contemplative and strategic ways. Lee and Mak (2008) note that teacher involvement in these practices go even further in activating metacognition learning through the use of setting personal goals and self-monitoring. In regard to reflective writing, students develop ownership of their own course of learning and writing through questioning.

Integrating collaborative tasks into learning increases open-

mindedness by introducing learners to confront and interact with differing perspectives through the use of group based activities. Collaborative tasks tend to challenge students in articulating ideas while being forced to take into consideration contrasting views of other members (Godley et al., 2006). According to Engberg and Hurtado (2011), these interactions force students to refine arguments, question biases, and reconsider positions. Furthermore, working in culturally diverse groups enables students to develop empathy and tolerance. With that said, integrating collaborative tasks do not come without challenges. Careful structuring is required in order to ensure that all voices of the group are heard and that more dominant personalities and opinions do not overshadow others. However, when collaborative tasks are integrated effectively, they can create learning environments where students are emboldened to become active contributors, enhancing their capacity for critical thought.

Cultural Influences on Critical Thinking in Foreign Language Learning

IMPACT OF CULTURAL BACKGROUND ON LEARNING STYLES

Research consistently demonstrates that cultural backgrounds shape a student's approach to learning. Perkins, D.N., Jay, E., and Tishman, S (1993) argue that the growth of dispositions cannot be examined by viewing learning in an isolated dimension. Dispositions are deeply grounded in systems of belief, values, and attitudes, in which culture needs to be taken into account. In fact, thinking can be categorized as a social activity, due to it

being shared as a group though internalized individually. Brown, Collins, and Duguid (1989) go further to define learning as a type of enculturation. Through living and observing within a designated culture, students gradually adapt and adopt behavioral and belief systems linked to the location of acquisition. Dispositional analysis is so closely linked to culturally based perspectives due to that they are acquired in the same method that learning is enculturated. These methods are institutional, such as political or school cultures, and interpersonal levels, such as interacting with peers or experienced individuals of society. Dimensions of culture, such as collectivism versus individualism, power distance, and communication norms, also strongly influence how students perceive and interact with knowledge in educational settings.

Atkinson (1997) highlights that students from collectivist cultures, such as Japan, China, and South Korea, where respect for authority is emphasized, may hesitate to question instructors. While this can be seen as a sign of respect, it can be problematic due to the inability to critically examine established ideas. This cultural disposition can lead to challenges in engaging with critical thinking tasks, especially open debates where questioning is a fundamental component of the critical inquiry process.

Conversely, students from individualist cultural backgrounds, such as France, Germany, Spain, and Portugal, where self-expression and independence are typically encouraged, may approach critical thinking activities more efficiently. Halx and Reybold (2005) observe that students from these backgrounds often enter classroom discussions with a readiness to assert their

opinions and engage in debate. Cultural differences in comfort levels in regard to confrontation and debate highlight how different backgrounds inhibit or facilitate students' engagement with critical analysis and reasoning practices.

Furthermore, Engber and Hurtado (2011) found that students exposed to culturally pluralistic environments were more likely to develop open-mindedness. According to their findings, interactions in diverse educational settings encourage students to consider alternative viewpoints. Kakai (2000) emphasizes the influence of power distance on learning styles, noting that students from high power distance cultures, such as Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and India, where hierarchy is emphasized, may avoid critical discussions. Individuals from these countries might also defer to the instructor's authority, often viewing critical inquiry as confrontational. This contrasts with students from low power distance cultures, such as Germany, Austria, and Norway, where questioning authority may be seen as part of the learning process. According to Kakai (2000), being exposed to cross-cultural studies will gradually encourage students from hierarchical backgrounds to adopt more critical thinking practices by highlighting respectful ways to engage with knowledge that does not compromise cultural values.

These insights underscore the importance of culturally sensitive teaching practices in fostering critical thinking across diverse student populations. By recognizing and adapting to cultural differences in learning styles, educators can create an inclusive environment that supports critical engagement for all

students, regardless of cultural background.

CHALLENGES IN CROSS-CULTURAL CLASSROOMS

Cross-cultural settings present significant challenges to fostering critical thinking dispositions, as cultural expectations seem to often shape students' comfort levels with independent analysis and inquiry. Cummins (2009) notes that students from hierarchical cultures, where authority is highly respected, may seem to resist activities that encourage debate or critique, as these practices conflict with ingrained cultural norms around value for educators and authority. On the other hand, Atkinson (1997) observes that cultures valuing individualism seem to permit unconstrained individual expression. When said activity exists, individual conflict and competition are inevitable. In fact, in individualistic cultures the concept of critical inquiry assumes that conflict and dissention are social realities.

Studies, including those by Gu, Wang, and Mason (2017), further show that students in cross-cultural classrooms often exhibit reluctance in engaging with tasks that require subjective interpretation or self-expression. These tasks, however, are crucial for fostering critical thinking and developing independent viewpoints. Students accustomed to teacher-led, memorization-based methods might struggle to adapt to teaching approaches that prioritize open-ended questions, and personal reflection. This is a result of instructional methods requiring self-directed learning and interpretation rather than using factual recall. In particular, students from collective cultures prioritize group

consensus over individual expression, limiting their willingness to contribute unique ideas or challenge commonly held beliefs.

The language barrier can also exacerbate these challenges, impacting students' readiness to participate in critical discussions. Pessoa and Freitas (2012) note that students learning a foreign language may prioritize linguistic accuracy and adherence to formal structures over exploratory thought as they focus on mastering language fundamentals. This emphasis on precision can hinder students' engagement with abstract or hypothetical questions. Language learners may fear making mistakes in front of peers or instructors, limiting their participation in activities requiring speculative thinking or subjective responses.

To mitigate these barriers, educators must consider culturally sensitive approaches that support critical inquiry without conflicting with students' cultural values. Pessoa and Freitas (2012) recommend adopting questioning techniques that respect students' cultural backgrounds while gradually encouraging independent thought. For example, educators might use scaffolding techniques to guide students toward more open-ended thinking instead of directly challenging a students' view. This approach helps them to feel comfortable exploring ideas critically, knowing their contributions are valued and respected. Cummins (2009) also advocates for creating classroom environments that emphasize collaborative learning, where students can engage in critical thinking in a supportive, group-oriented context. This method could align with collectivist values while gently encouraging students to express individual perspectives within a

shared learning experience.

Overall, overcoming these challenges requires educators to balance respecting cultural norms with methods that encourage independent thinking. By using culturally adaptive questioning and fostering inclusive environments, educators can find ways to support cross-cultural students in developing critical thinking skills. Creating a supportive environment will also allow them to bridge cultural divides while becoming reflective, independent thinkers.

CULTURAL ADAPTATION OF PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES

Culturally adaptive methodologies are essential for helping students from diverse backgrounds to engage confidently in critical thinking practices. Such approaches take in to account students' cultural norms and values, bridging traditional learning preferences and independent, analytical thinking demands. Engberg and Hurtado (2011) emphasize that reflective practices, such as journaling, can effectively encourage open-mindedness and self-reflection in multicultural classrooms. Through reflective journaling, students are able to process their thoughts before sharing. Doing this can help students' unfamiliar with open debate develop their ideas in a way that is less intimidating. Paired discussions, which allow learners to explore ideas in one-to-one settings, further encourage engagement by creating safer, more intimate environments for expressing views.

Culturally responsive questioning is another vital strategy. Rather than presenting direct challenges to students' perspectives,

educators can use questions to invite students to relate concepts to their cultural experiences. By connecting new ideas to familiar cultural frameworks, students are encouraged to expand their thinking in ways that feel relevant and accessible. Cummins (2009) advocates incorporating culturally familiar examples and references in instruction to introduce complex ideas. This approach respects students' existing knowledge structures while encouraging them to consider broader applications.

Moreover, language plays a significant role in culturally adaptive pedagogy, particularly in classrooms with non-native speakers. Cummins (2009) highlights the benefits of allowing students to use their first language when grappling with complex concepts. By enabling students to process information in their primary language, educators reduce the cognitive load associated with foreign language learning. This strategy eases comprehension and fosters more significant engagement with the material, as students have access to draw on their entire linguistic repertoire to explore and discuss ideas.

For example, students might initially discuss a critical concept in their first language before transitioning to the target language. This process supports the development of critical dispositions like open-mindedness and curiosity by removing language barriers that might inhibit participation. Incorporating their first language can also serve as a cognitive scaffold in bilingual or multilingual settings (Cummins, 2009). Using the first language allows students to process complex ideas more effectively before articulating them into the target language.

In addition to these strategies, setting culturally relevant expectations can further support students' development of critical thinking dispositions. Cummins (2009) argues that by aligning instructional methods and assessment criteria with students' cultural backgrounds, educators foster inclusive environments that encourage cognitive exploration without being forced to abandon familiar values or learning styles. Gradually, students become more comfortable in engaging in critical analysis, seeing it as a natural extension of their educational journey rather than a departure from cultural norms. This approach is so important in foreign language learning, where students may already be facing challenges with self-expression and cultural adaptation.

In conclusion, culturally adaptive pedagogical strategies enable educators to respect and incorporate students' cultural backgrounds while promoting critical thinking. Reflective journaling, paired discussions, culturally responsive questioning, and strategic use of their first language all help to create an inclusive, supportive learning environment where students are empowered to engage in critical inquiry.

Challenges in Teaching Critical Thinking Dispositions

TEACHER PREPAREDNESS AND BELIEFS

Teachers' beliefs and preparedness significantly impacts their ability to foster critical thinking dispositions in multicultural foreign language classrooms. Research by Kubanyiova and Feryok (2015) highlight that many educators lack formal training in

culturally responsive teaching and critical thinking pedagogy. Without understanding these areas, teachers may inadvertently default to teacher-centered, authoritative instructional methods, especially if they believe students are unaccustomed to critical engagement (Pessoa & Freitas, 2012). Bunch (2013), notes that this is compounded by the fact that most teachers have very little training in working with learners. Furthermore, teachers who are not accustomed to fostering inquiry or open debate may struggle to model these skills effectively.

In contrast, teachers trained in culturally adaptive pedagogical strategies are likelier to encourage self-reflection, inquiry, and other critical dispositions in students. These educators recognize that fostering critical thinking requires sensitivity to students' backgrounds and an understanding of how cultural values shape their learning styles. These educators also emphasize open dialogue, varied assessment methods, and collaborative projects to support diverse perspectives (Macaro, 2006).

INSTITUTIONAL AND POLICY BARRIERS

Systemic issues in educational institutions can also restrict the promotion of critical thinking dispositions. In many foreign language programs, rigid curriculum and exam focused policies limit the instructors' flexibility in implementing innovative teaching methods. Studies by Norris (1989) indicate that standardized testing pressures lead students' to focus on rote memorization and linguistic accuracy over critical engagement. Educators in Japan, for example, often face pressures from exam-

driven language curricula that prioritize vocabulary and grammar at the expense of critical discourse (Cummins, 2009).

Moreover, institutional support for professional development in critical thinking pedagogy is often limited. Teachers may not have access to resources or training needed to effectively integrate culturally responsive and critical thinking oriented instruction. Without administrative support, educators may find it challenging to adapt their teaching to foster critical dispositions in multicultural language settings (Norris, 1989).

Discussion

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

This review has demonstrated that fostering critical thinking dispositions in foreign language learning requires a shift from conventional, rote-based strategies to more dynamic, culturally adaptive pedagogies. The traditional grammar translation and memorization based approaches, lacks the depth necessary for nurturing higher-order dispositions (Macaro, 2006; Cummins, 2009). By focusing solely on linguistic accuracy, these methods do not engage students in reflective or analytical thinking, limiting their ability to connect linguistic content to broader contexts.

Conversely, innovative strategies such as inquiry based learning and reflective practices show significant promise for cultivating critical thinking dispositions in diverse classrooms. Inquiry based learning encourages active participation where students develop the habit of posing questions and delving deeper into subject matter, supporting dispositions like inquisitiveness

and systematic thinking (Lee & Mak, 2018). Reflective practices, such as journaling and self-assessment, enhance metacognitive awareness and contribute to developing cognitive maturity and openness (Martinez, 2006). These methods prompt students to move beyond basic rote learning by evaluating their thought processes, thereby nurturing the critical thinking skills necessary for language learning.

Cultural context has a profound impact on students' engagement with critical thinking activities. For example, students from collectivist cultures, such as East Asia, may exhibit reluctance to challenge authority or participate in debates (Atkinson, 1997). This can inhibit their development of dispositions like open-mindedness and analytic thinking. In contrast, individualistic cultures, such as those found in parts of Europe, encourage students to express their opinions and engage more assertively in classroom discussions (Halx & Reybold, 2005).

However, the review also highlights significant systemic and institutional challenges. Barriers such as exam-centric curricula and insufficient teacher training in critical thinking pedagogy constrain the development of critical dispositions (Kubanyiova & Feryok, 2015). The pressure to adhere to standardized testing norms can limit teachers' ability to implement innovative instructional practices that emphasize critical engagement.

To overcome these challenges, educators should integrate culturally adaptive teaching methods that align with students' backgrounds while promoting critical inquiry. Strategies such as collaborative learning tasks and reflective journaling can bridge

cultural and linguistic divisions (Engberg & Hurtado, 2011). Additionally, professional development programs focusing on critical thinking and culturally responsive pedagogy are crucial for empowering educators to effectively guide students in cultivating these dispositions.

By combining inquiry based approaches, reflective practices, and collaborative learning, teachers can create well-rounded, supportive learning environments, encouraging deeper, analytical engagement. Addressing the gaps in teacher training and curriculum design through targeted institutional support can further enhance the teaching of critical thinking in multicultural foreign language classrooms. This comprehensive approach is essential for preparing students to navigate the complex, intercultural landscape of language learning with a critical acuity and open-minded perspective.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATORS

Based on the comprehensive finding of this review, educators are encouraged to adopt and integrate several key practices to enhance critical thinking. First, reflective practices such as guided journaling, peer reviews, and self-assessment exercises should be incorporated regularly (Martinez, 2006). Carrell (1989) notes that these activities prompt students to evaluate their cognitive processes, leading to improved metacognitive awareness and intellectual maturity. Reflective practices foster cognitive flexibility, allowing students to reconsider their assumptions and approach problems with a more balanced and open-minded

perspective.

Second, collaborative tasks offer as an effective tool for promoting critical thinking dispositions. Activities that require students to work together, such as in group discussions, debate formats, and collaborative projects, expose learners to diverse points of view, encouraging them to articulate and defend their ideas (Godley et al., 2006). These activities not only develop empathy but also improve analytic skills through pushing students to consider various arguments critically (Engberg & Hurtado, 2011).

Third, inquiry-based learning should be a core part of the curriculum to cultivate dispositions like inquisitiveness and systematicity. Teachers can design lessons that encourage students to ask questions, investigate solutions, and explore subjects deeply. Lee and Mak (2018) note that educators should also practice culturally responsive questioning, which involve using culturally familiar examples and references to help students understand complex concepts and to feel more comfortable engaging in discussions (Cummins, 2009). This approach respects the cultural context of students', making it easier to bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and new, more complex material.

Recognizing and accommodating cultural differences in learners critical thinking approaches is important. Instructors must be aware that students from different cultures might initially be less inclined to voice dissent or challenge ideas openly (Gu, Wang, & Mason, 2017). Therefore, educators should create a supportive environment where all students feel safe expressing

their opinions and gradually adapt to more participative learning styles. Again, structured scaffolding, where students build confidence through incremental steps, can help in this adaptation.

INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

To facilitate the implementation of these strategies, institutions should offer robust professional development programs that focus on culturally adaptive critical thinking pedagogy. Training sessions should equip educators with the tools to navigate diverse classrooms effectively, while encourage innovative practices that align with critical thinking goals (Kubanyiova & Feryok, 2015). Furthermore, institutions can assist in bridging resource gaps such as guides, case studies, and workshops that focus on integrating dispositions into everyday teaching.

Educational institutions must also support the balance between meeting standardized curriculum requirements and adopting innovative approaches. While exam focused programs often limit flexibility, schools should incorporate reflective and inquiry-based practices within structured content (Norris, 1989). Administrators should promote an environment where educators are empowered to use adaptive strategies, blending traditional instruction with modern, student-centered practices that foster critical thinking.

By implementing these recommendations, educators create comprehensive learning environments that nurture critical thinking dispositions and support the development of students. Emphasizing inquiry, reflection, and collaboration ensures that

students are not only absorbing knowledge but also actively engaging with content in ways that enhance their cognitive and analytical capabilities (Kubanyiova & Feryok, 2015). This approach prepares students to navigate complex cultural and linguistic landscapes with intellectual confidence and adaptability.

Conclusion

This review has examined the critical thinking dispositions necessary for effective language learning in multicultural environments and has identified several pedagogical strategies that support critical thinking dispositions. The evidence reveals that fostering critical dispositions, such as inquisitiveness, open-mindedness, and systematic thinking, often require nuanced, culturally adaptive approaches, acknowledging the cultural backgrounds of students' educational experience. As foreign language educators seek to integrate these critical dispositions, they encounter challenges related to cultural values, teacher preparedness, and institutional constraints. However, educators can bridge these differences by adopting culturally responsive frameworks, creating learning environments that encourage deep analytical engagement.

One way to address this is to combine inquiry-based learning, reflective practices, and culturally responsive questioning to create a supportive classroom environment embracing students to engage in diverse critical analysis. For example, Cummins (2009) advocates for integrating native languages strategically to facilitate comprehension and cognitive engagement. Likewise,

Engberg and Hurtado (2011) emphasize the importance of structured reflective practices, such as journaling and paired discussions, allowing students to process information before sharing publicly. These approaches and collaborative activities support intellectual curiosity, and cognitive flexibility.

Moreover, this study also revealed that significant challenges remain. Many educational institutions prioritize the use of standardized testing and rote memorization over critical engagement. Norris (1989) highlighted that exam-focused curricula often restricts educators from exploring critical thinking pedagogy, emphasizing vocabulary retention over cognitive exploration. Kubanyiova and Feryok (2015) recommend professional development initiatives that prepare educators to apply adaptive teaching methods in multicultural settings, promoting inclusive, inquiry-based classroom environments. By addressing these barriers through institutional support, such as advanced training on culturally responsive pedagogy, and being flexible with language curricula, instructors will be able to incorporate critical thinking frameworks.

Moving forward, empirical studies, specifically longitudinal research, are needed to evaluate long-term impacts of critical thinking dispositions in foreign language learning. Understanding how dispositions such as open-mindedness and analytic rigor develop over time and across proficiency levels would help to provide valuable insights. While challenges still persist, adopting culturally adaptive, disposition-oriented frameworks present a promising approach to enhancing critical thinking in foreign

language education. As educators continue to explore a multitude of methods, a commitment to ongoing research and institutional support will be essential in advancing language education that will build linguistic proficiency and that nurtures critical thinkers capable of navigating complex multicultural landscapes.

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